

The policies issued especially for the private sector economy in China since 1982 till 2022

Hind El Atmani¹

School of International Economics and Trade, Shandong University of Finance and Economics, Jinan, China

Abstract

Since the reform and opening up, the private economy has been re-born and has seen great development in China. Along with the development of the private economy, the party's policies on the private economy have also gradually matured and improved. The evolution of the Party's private economy and policies can be divided into four stages. It is of certain practical significance to review and sort out this evolutionary process, summarize its historical experience, and draw useful inspiration from it, in order to further promote the development of the individual private economy and build socialism with Chinese characteristics.

Keywords: Private Sector, Policy, China, Economy

Introduction

In the early stages of Chinese socialism, it was built by private investment and owned by private ownership, and there was an economic component of employment-labor relations. Under socialist conditions, it is connected to the dominant public economy and is greatly affected by it. To a certain extent, the development of the private economy in China is conducive to the following: the integration of capital, technology, and labor; the formation of social productive forces as soon as possible; the promotion of production development; the active market; the provision of employment opportunities in many aspects; better meeting the needs of the people in many aspects; and the growth of business talents. It is a necessary and beneficial supplement to the public economy, and it has the inevitability of its existence for a long time. After 1956, China did not allow the existence of the private economy for a period of time, which constrained the development of social productive forces and the socialist commodity economy to a certain extent. At the end of 1978, the Third Plenary Session of the 11th Central Committee of the Communist Party of China decided to implement the policy of opening up to the outside world and revitalizing the country. Since then, the private economy has developed to a certain extent. Since there is an employment-labor relationship in the private economy, it is inevitable to take possession of the remaining labor of others by virtue of ownership of the means of production. However, in China, the dominant position of the socialist public economy has been established, and the proportion of the private economy is very small. In 1986, the output value of urban private industry was 2.9 billion yuan, accounting for only 0.3% of the country's total industrial output value. In order to adapt to the external environment, some private economies have also adopted the methods of worker equity, labor dividends, democratic management, or retention of public accumulation. To deal with the negative effects of the private economy, the state can improve its guidance, supervision, and management through relevant

policies and laws. This way, the private economy can grow well and serve socialist construction more effectively.

1. The first stage: from "not recognizing and not allowing" to "looking and waiting," from negative constraints to allowing the existence of the private economy in policy.

From the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee to the end of 1986, the Party adopted a "look, wait, and see" policy for the private economy, watching its development and adopting the basic policy of "not promoting it, not publicizing it, and not hastily banning it," i.e., the Party's policy on the private economy changed from "look, wait, and see" to "look, wait, and see." In other words, the policy on the private economy has changed from a negative restriction to one that allows its existence.

For more than 20 years before the reform and opening up, the private economy and private entrepreneurs were not allowed to exist, and the original private economy was basically killed. After the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee, the Chinese Communist Party reverted to its line of thought of seeking truth from facts and began to adjust its economic policies. The private economy was reborn and developed from the embryo of the individual economy, and the relaxation of the Party's policy toward the private economy began with the individual economy. "After the end of the Cultural Revolution, millions of intellectual youths who had gone to the countryside returned to the city. At the same time, a large number of unemployed young people were living in the city, which made the job problems more visible. In March 1978, the State Council, in its report on the National Conference of Directors of Industry and Commerce, pointed out that in order to facilitate the lives of the masses and to solve the employment problems of some people, a part of the individual economy could be restored and developed in the cities and towns according to the current situation. The Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee of the People's Republic of China explicitly stipulated that "the community members' self-reserved land, family side businesses, and market trade are necessary supplements to the socialist

economy, and no one should interfere with them," and put forward the policy that "a few people should get rich first through honest labor"^[1]. In September 1979, the Fourth Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee of the Party adopted the Decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Several Issues Concerning the Acceleration of Agricultural Development, which clearly stated that "The multiple operations of the community teams are a socialist economy, and the community members' self-reserved land, self-reserved animals, family sideline businesses, and rural bazaar trade are subsidiary and supplementary to the socialist economy, and they must not be criticized as capitalist tails."^[2] Since then, the central government has issued a number of policies and laws to encourage and protect the individual economy. The Sixth Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee designated the individual economy as "a necessary supplement to the public economy", and the Twelfth National Congress in 1982 further pointed out that "there should be a variety of economic forms co-existing at the same time." At the Fifth Session of the Fifth National People's Congress, which took place in December 1982, the Constitution of the People's Republic of China was approved. It clearly states that "^[3] the individual economies of urban and rural workers, in accordance with the law, are a supplement to the socialist public economy." This affirmed the status and role of the individual economy in the form of law, and also created the necessary and suitable environment for the recovery and development of the private economy. With the permission, encouragement, and support of the Party and state policies, the individual economy rapidly recovered and developed nationwide, and those rural and urban-rural individual economies with more capital and larger production scale gradually developed into hired economies. As a result of inertia, some people at that time advocated "moving it a bit". The second generation leadership group with Deng Xiaoping as the core took a cautious attitude from the thought that "practice is the only criterion to test the truth". Deng Xiaoping repeatedly emphasized the need not to move, not to change, "to see the meaning of this unchanging in the context of the goals of the entire decades." ^[4] In 1982, according to Deng Xiaoping's suggestion, the Politburo of the Central Committee clearly pointed out,

after careful study, "This will not shock socialism; we can wait and see." ^[5] The policy of "taking a look" was in fact to allow and protect the phenomenon of hired labor, and the Central Government's Document No. 1 of January 2, 1983, "Some Issues of the Current Rural Economic Policy," pointed out that rural individual industrial and commercial households and competent people in the plantation industry should hire helpers and apprentices. If you want to stop people from hiring large families or businesses, don't advocate for it, don't publicize it, and don't rush to ban it.^[6] This is the well-known "do not advocate, do not prohibit, do not propagate" policy, which translates as "see as you go," "look and say," and "do not rush to simply deny or affirm." The "three no's" policy of the Party Central Committee respected the practice, the creativity, and the choice of the masses, and in fact, tacitly protected the sprouting and development of the private economy. In a speech on January 12, 1983, Deng Xiaoping said, "All work should contribute to the building of socialism with Chinese characteristics and should be measured by whether it is conducive to the prosperity and happiness of the people and the prosperity and development of the country." ^[7] On October 22, 1984, Deng Xiaoping said clearly at the third plenary session of the Central Advisory Committee: "The issue of hiring workers some time ago was quite a shock, and people were very worried. My opinion is to leave it for two years and then look at it." ^[8] This new change in theory and policy marked a breakthrough in the long-standing party policy of "not recognizing and not allowing" the private economy, which was "resolutely outlawed and immediately banned" and developed into a policy of "wait and see and acquiesce." This marked the beginning of the thawing of the long-frozen private economic policy and actually gave the green light to the development of the private economy.

2. Second stage: The legal status of the private economy was recognized, and "a supplement to the socialist public economy" was proposed, and the policy on the private economy was changed from basically single encouragement to a combination of encouragement and management guidance.

From 1987 to 1991, China's private economy entered a new period of development. With the innovation of the theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics, the Party gradually deepened its understanding of the private economy, advanced the "complementary theory," and shifted its private-economy policy from a single encouragement to a combination of encouragement and management guidance. With the acquiescence of the "take a look" and "three no's" policies, the private economy developed greatly. Following the practice and observation of development during these years, the Party's understanding and policies on the private economy became increasingly clear, and the policies on the private economy shifted from a single encouragement to a combination of encouragement and management guidance. In January 1987, the Central Committee Document No. 5 "on Leading Rural Reform to Deepen" clearly pointed out: "In the primary stage of socialist society, in the development of the commodity economy, over a longer period of time, the existence of an individual economy and a small number of private enterprises is inevitable." Certain private enterprises that employ more than a limited number of workers in order to expand the scale of operation "should also be allowed to exist, strengthen the management, promote the benefits and suppress the disadvantages, and gradually guide the policy." ^[9]. This was the first time that the legitimacy of the private economy was established in a Party document, providing a policy guarantee for the existence of the private economy, and the Thirteenth Party Congress held in October 1987 clearly elaborated on the status, nature, and role of the private economy and for the first time used the concept of "private economy." This was followed by: "A certain degree of development of the private economy is conducive to promoting production, activating the market, expanding employment, and better meeting people's multifaceted needs, and is a necessary and useful supplement to the public economy." The private economy is a necessary and useful supplement to the public sector economy and must be formulated as soon as possible with policies and laws on the private economy to protect their legitimate rights and interests, and strengthen their guidance, supervision, and management.

^[10] This was the first time in the history of the Party that the National Congress affirmed the existence of

the ownership structure of the private economy at the primary stage of socialism and allowed that the share could vary in different industries and regions, a qualitative leap in the Party's understanding of the private economy. In accordance with the recommendations of the 13th National Congress, in April 1988, the First Session of the Seventh National People's Congress adopted an amendment to the Constitution, which provided that: "The State allows the existence and development of the private economy within the limits prescribed by law, and the private economy is a supplement to the socialist public economy. The state protects the legitimate rights and interests of the private economy and exercises guidance, supervision, and management over the private economy. " ^[11] For the first time, the legal status of the private economy was written into the Constitution. For the first time, the private economy was recognized by the fundamental law of the state, indicating that the Party's understanding of the private economy had risen to a new stage. Then, the State Council promulgated three administrative regulations one after another, namely, the Provisional Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Private Enterprises, the Rules for the Implementation of the Provisional Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Income Tax for Private Enterprises, and the Regulations of the State Council on the Collection of Personal Income Adjustment Tax for Investors in Private Enterprises. The strengthening of the protection and management of private enterprises marked the formal entry of the private economy as an independent economic component in China's economic and social life. On the one hand, China's economy has been undergoing a complete restructuring since the beginning of 1989; on the other hand, after the "89 political turmoil", the once silent public opinion against the private economy resurfaced. Due to the impact of domestic and foreign political factors, the private economy was languishing and moving forward slowly. In response to this situation, Jiang Zemin clearly pointed out in 1989: "Our policy is, first, to encourage them to develop actively within the scope allowed by the state; second, to use economic, administrative, and legal means to strengthen management and guidance so as to give full play to their positive role while limiting their negative factors that are not conducive to socialist economic development." ^[12] At the end of 1991, the

Central Committee pointed out in Document No. 15 that the private economy will exist and develop for a fairly long historical period, and the present private entrepreneurs should not be simply compared and equated with the industrial and commercial people of the past, let alone subjected to socialist transformation as they were in the 1950s. In part because of the efforts of the Party Central Committee, the status of the private economy started to rise again over time.

3. Third stage: the "component theory" of the socialist market economy was proposed, and the policy on the private economy changed from allowing the coexistence of multiple economic components to the long-term common development of multiple ownership economies.

From 1992 to 2001, Chinese characteristics continued to make breakthroughs and innovations, and the Party's understanding of the private economy became more profound, gradually forming the "component theory," from allowing the coexistence of multiple economic components to the long-term common development of multiple ownership economies. Although the 14th National Congress, which was held in October 1992 under the guidance of Deng Xiaoping's Southern Talks, still stipulated the status of the private economy as a "supplement", it clearly stipulated that "the goal of China's economic system reform is to establish a socialist market economy system", and stated that "the private economy is a socialist market economy." It also pointed out that "in the ownership structure, the public ownership system, including the national ownership system and collective ownership system as the main body, the individual economy, private economy, and foreign investment economy as a supplement, the long-term common development of a variety of economic components can voluntarily implement multiple forms of joint operation." ^[13] The proposal of "common development" has diluted the meaning of the private economy as a "complementary" supporting role and taken a big step forward to the "component theory". In November 1993, the Third Plenary Session of the 14th CPC Central Committee adopted the Decision of the CPC Central Committee on Several Issues Concerning the Establishment of a Socialist Market

Economy System, which clearly put forward the policy of "adhering to the public ownership system as the main body and the common development of various economic components." policy, but also pointed out that "for the whole country, the public ownership system should occupy the main position in the national economy. Some places, some industries can be different states to create conditions for all kinds of economic systems to participate equally in market competition, and for all kinds of enterprises to treat all types of enterprises equally." ^[14] At the same time, it was pointed out that "small state-owned enterprises in general can be contracted, leased, some can be reorganized into joint-stock cooperative systems, or can be sold to collectives and individuals." ^[15] The decision proposed for the first time that the state treats state-owned economies, private economies, and other types of ownership "equally" and participates in market competition on an equal footing, which is a huge leap in understanding. Following that, the State also said that the Company Law, the Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Company Registration, the Labor Law of the People's Republic of China, and the Provisional Regulations of the People's Republic of China on Enterprise Income Tax were all the same for businesses of all kinds. This helped the private economy grow in a healthy way. The 15th Party Congress, held in September 1997, was a landmark conference for the private economy. The 15th Congress clearly defined the basic economic system of China's primary stage of socialism and confirmed that the non-public economy is an important part of China's socialist market economy. The 15th Five-Year Plan proposed that "the public ownership system is the mainstay, and the joint development of the economy of multiple ownership systems is a basic economic system at the primary stage of socialism in China," and further proposed that "the non-public economy is an important part of China's socialist market economy." ^[16] "The non-public economy is an important part of China's socialist market economy."^[16] "Non-public ownership is an important part of China's socialist market economy."^[17] A group of people who work together called the National United Front Work Conference again said that "the non-public economy, such as the private sector, should be encouraged and guided, so that it can grow well, play a full and positive role,"^[18] The

introduction of the "component theory" means that the private economy has changed from a supporting role as a "complement" to a "family", from "outside the system" to "inside the system". It has become part of the socialist market economy, marking a major leap in the Party's theory of the private economy. In March 1999, the Second Session of the Ninth National People's Congress passed constitutional amendments, clearly stipulating that "the non-public economy, such as the individual economy and the private economy, within the scope of the law, is an important part of the socialist market economy" and that "the state protects The State protects the legitimate rights and interests of the individual economy and the private economy. The state guides, supervises, and manages the individual and private economy. "

^[19]In this way, the Constitution, in the form of a fundamental law, establishes the basic economic system and form of distribution at the primary stage of socialism in China and affirms that the private economy and other non-public economies are an important part of the socialist market economy. While vigorously developing the private economy, the party also made new assertions in practice about the essential attributes of private entrepreneurs. On December 4, 2000, Jiang Zemin clearly pointed out at the National United Front Work Conference: "In the process of reform and opening up, under the guidance of the Party's policy of enriching the people, individual workers and private entrepreneurs who have first become rich through honest labor and lawful operation are also glorious." They have contributed to the cause of building socialism with Chinese characteristics and should be respected by society. " ^[20] In the 2001 July 1 Speech, it was not only proposed that private entrepreneurs are the builders of socialism with Chinese characteristics, but it was also pointed out that private entrepreneurs can also join the Party. These new statements are the first scientific assertions in the history of the CPC on the social status of private enterprise owners in the primary stage of socialism and are conducive to unifying the Party's understanding of the essential attributes of the new social class of private enterprise owners.

4. Fourth stage: the "equality theory" is proposed, and the policy on the private economy is upgraded from a "policy" to a "basic economic system".

Since the 16th Party Congress in 2002, the Party has put forward the policy of "unwavering" development of the private economy, and the report of the 16th Congress has clearly stated that "excellent members of private enterprise owners are allowed to join the Party" and has put forward many new policies and views, making it more systematic and mature. The Party's theory of the private economy has become a "theory of equality", and the policy on the private economy has been upgraded from a "policy" to a "basic economic system". The report of the 16th Party Congress in 2002 comprehensively summarized the theoretical guidelines and policies that have guided the healthy development of the non-public economy since the reform and opening up, systematically expounded the Party's policy guidelines for the development of the non-public economy, including the private economy, in the new historical period, and further confirmed and fully affirmed the economic, political, and social status of the private economy and private entrepreneurs in the primary stage of socialism, reflecting another qualitative leap in the Party's theory of the private economy. This is another qualitative leap in the Party's theory of the private economy.

(1) It is clearly proposed that the non-public economy is not opposed to the public economy, and that the basic economic system, in which the public system is the mainstay and the economies of various types of ownership develop together, should be adhered to and improved, and that "two unshakable principles" should be put forward, namely, "the public economy must be consolidated and developed without wavering" and "the public economy must be developed without wavering." must not waver in encouraging, supporting, and guiding the development of the non-public sector of the economy. The individual, private, and other forms of non-public economy are an important part of the socialist market economy and play an important role in fully mobilizing the enthusiasm of all sectors of society and

accelerating the development of the productive forces. " ^[21] This marks the Party's theory of the private economy and other non-public economies as maturing.

(2) Emphasis on "improving the legal system for the protection of private property." The report of the Sixteenth National Congress states, "All labor that benefits the people and society must be respected and protected." "All legitimate labor income and legitimate non-labor income should be protected."^[22] This was the first time in the history of the Party that the protection of private property was most directly and explicitly proposed. When the Constitution was changed after the 16th Congress, the legal system for protecting private property got even better constitutionally.

(3) The Party openly confirmed the nature of the class of private business owners, so that the political status of people in the non-public economy was established for the first time. The 16th National Congress proposed that the entrepreneurial activities of all kinds of investors should be encouraged, and all legitimate labor and non-labor income should be protected. The presence or absence of property or the amount of property should not be the only thing we use to judge people's political progress or backwardness. We should also look at their ideological and political conditions and real-world performance, how they got their property and how they use and dispose of it, and how much they have contributed to the cause of socialism with Chinese characteristics with their own labor.^[23]

(4) It was publicly stated that the best members of the private enterprise owner class could join the party. The report of the 16th National Congress absorbed the spirit of Jiang Zemin's "July 1 speech" in 2001 and pointed out for the first time in the political report of the National Party Congress that "advanced elements from other social strata who recognize the Party's program and constitution, who consciously struggle for the Party's line and program, who have been tested for a long time, and who meet the conditions for party membership should be absorbed into the Party." This assertion of "absorbing private entrepreneurs into the party" is another new breakthrough in the theory of the private economy, which has greatly enhanced

the social influence and class base of the Party. In September 2003, the Party held the Third Plenary Session of the 16th Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and adopted the Decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Several Issues Concerning the Perfection of the Socialist Market Economy System, which stated: "Relax market access and allow non-public capital to enter infrastructure, public utilities, and other industries and fields not prohibited by laws and regulations." Non-public enterprises enjoy the same treatment as other enterprises in terms of investment and financing, taxation, land use and foreign trade ^[25]. and reiterated that "individual, private, and other non-public economies are an important force in promoting the development of China's social productive forces." ^[26] This means "equal competition in the economy." In March 2004, the Second Session of the Tenth National People's Congress adopted the Amendment to the Constitution of the People's Republic of China, which amended Article 13 of the Constitution to read: "The state protects citizens' lawful income, savings, and ownership of houses and other lawful property" and "The state protects citizens' right to inherit private property in accordance with the law" to "Citizens' lawful private property shall be inviolable" and "the state protects the private property rights of citizens and the right of inheritance in accordance with the provisions of the law." The state may expropriate or requisition the private property of citizens for the needs of the public interest in accordance with the provisions of the law and provide compensation. ^[27] Here, it shows that the Constitution has made it so that the private property of private businesses is safe. In February 2005, the State Council issued the "Several Opinions of the State Council on Encouraging, Supporting, and Guiding the Development of Individual Private and Other Non-public Economies" ("Article 36 of the Non-public Economy"), which was formally introduced, stipulating in seven aspects that no unit or individual may infringe upon the lawful property of non-public enterprises and may not illegally change the property ownership relationship. From relaxing market access for the non-public economy, increasing fiscal and financial support for the non-public economy, improving social services for the non-public economy, safeguarding the legitimate rights and interests of non-public

enterprises and workers, guiding non-public enterprises to improve their quality, improving government supervision of non-public enterprises, and strengthening guidance and policy coordination for the development of the non-public economy, The "36 Articles on Non-Public Economy" are the first central government documents to promote the development of the non-public economy since the founding of New China, removing institutional barriers to the development of the non-public economy and providing a theoretical basis for the development of the private economy in a wider range of fields. In March 2007, the Fifth Session of the Tenth National People's Congress passed the Property Rights Law and the Enterprise Income Tax Law. The former clearly stipulates that the equal legal status and development rights of all market subjects are guaranteed. The property rights of the state, collectives, private individuals, and other right holders are protected by law and may not be infringed upon by any unit or individual. In 2007, the 17th Party Congress formally put forward the theory of "equality," that is, equal protection in law and equal competition in the economy. This means that, under socialist conditions, the private economy is not only "an important part of the market economy," but also receives equal treatment with the public economy, treating them equally and competing on an equal footing. The Party's theory of the private economy has made a new leap.

5. The current situation of Chinese private sector policy

Under the new leadership of Xi, the country will unswervingly encourage, support, and guide the development of the non-public sector and support private enterprises to develop towards a broader stage. President Xi confirmed the contribution of the private sector to Chinese economic development: "Over the past 40 years, the private sector of the economy has become an indispensable force behind China's development." "China's private sector has played an important role in bolstering economic growth, promoting innovation, creating jobs, and improving people's wellbeing." Xi asked for policies and measures to be taken in six areas to make it easier for private businesses to grow and solve problems.

First, the burden of taxes and fees on the companies should be eased. Substantial tax cuts, including the elimination of value-added taxes, should be pursued, with tax breaks available for micro and small businesses, as well as technological companies. The nominal rates for social security contributions should be reduced to reflect current situations. Second, steps should be taken to overcome the difficulties and high cost of private-sector financing. Financial market thresholds should be decreased in order to broaden private enterprises' fund-raising avenues. Third, the playing field should be level for private firms that follow the direction of the country's economic upgrading and have high prospects. Various hidden constraints and impediments to private enterprise should be addressed. A level playing field should be created for private firms in market access, administrative approvals, commercial operations, bids and tenders, and military-civil integration. Participation of private corporations in the reform of state-owned enterprises is encouraged. Fourth, policy implementation needs to be strengthened. Policies should be better coordinated and precisely implemented in order to give private enterprises a greater sense of fulfillment. The same criteria should be followed for firms of all types of ownership when it comes to minimizing overcapacity and leverage. Authorities should not use a one-size-fits-all approach to law enforcement when it comes to workplace safety and the environment. Fifth, a new form of amicable and clean connection should be established between government and business. Party bodies and administrations at all levels should devote more time and energy to private firms and entrepreneurs, listen to their concerns and requests, and take steps to assist them in resolving problems. Major policies should be correctly stated, and certain incorrect assertions should be corrected. Sixth, the personal and property safety of entrepreneurs should be ensured. When they do their job, disciplinary and supervisory authorities should not only solve cases but also protect people and businesses' legitimate rights and the lawful operation of businesses. Statistical information from the State Administration of Market Supervision and Administration shows that from 2012 to 2021, the number of private enterprises in China grew from 10,857,000 to 44,575,000, quadrupling in 10 years, and the proportion of private enterprises in

the total number of enterprises increased from 79.4% to 92.1%.The number of private enterprises has quadrupled in 10 years. The private sector contributed more than 60 percent of China's GDP growth and over half of China's fiscal revenue. More than 60 percent of China's fixed-asset investment and outbound investment has been made by private investors. From the 18th Party Congress, from emphasizing the "inviolability" of the property rights of the public and non-public economy, to improving the property rights protection system with fairness as the core principle, to introducing various policies and initiatives to stimulate the entrepreneurial spirit and encourage and support the private economy, the private economy encourages, supports, and guides the development of the non-public economy. The policy system to support and guide the development of the non-public economy has been further improved and the policy environment further optimized. The majority of private enterprises have played an important role in stabilizing growth, promoting innovation, increasing employment, and improving people's livelihoods. Over the past 40 years, China's private economy has grown tenaciously from scratch and from small to large. Through these changing "buzz words", people can feel the private economy contributing to China's economic development and bringing vitality through "go to sea", "individual," "million yuan household", "shareholding cooperation," "Internet entrepreneurship," and "shareholding cooperation." Undoubtedly, the Party and the State support the development of the private economy in a clear, consistent, and deepening way. The private economy is not able to help the appendage, but it is an important part of the socialist market economy and a foundation for China's economic and social growth in the long run. The private economy is born as a result of reform and opening up, and it thrives as a result of reform and opening up.It is well proven that reform and opening up have greatly changed the faces of the Chinese people and allowed them to find the key to the door to integrate into the trend of the times. Today, the pace of reform will not stop, the door can no longer be closed. This is the direction of the people, but also the right path. Whenever private enterprises encounter difficulties, the Party and the State always do everything possible to solve their problems. At present, the downward pressure on the economy

is greater, the international situation is more severe, complex and uncertain, and private enterprises face many challenges, especially the development of smaller small and medium-sized microenterprises under greater pressure. At the March 16 meeting of the State Council Financial Stability Development Committee, it was stressed that "adherence to deepen reform, expand openness, adhere to the market, the principle of the rule of law, adhere to "two unwavering" and effectively protect property rights." In recent times, in accordance with the requirements of the executive meeting of the State Council, relevant departments have acted to implement the large-scale VAT tax rebate as soon as possible and send "real money" to enterprises. The development and growth of private enterprises also needs a good public opinion environment. Speculation about the "private economy leaving the field theory" has caused a panic in the market and shaken the expectations of the entrepreneurial community in China's economy in recent years. This is something that needs to be kept an eye on and must be publicly opposed.

Conclusion

To sum up, the private economy plays a very important role in China's economic development. There is a saying that the private economy contributes more than 50% of China's economic tax revenue, more than 60% of GDP, more than 70% of technological innovation achievements, more than 80% of urban labor and employment, and more than 90% of the number of enterprises. This shows, from one side, that the private economy is very prominent. However, China's leadership cannot ignore the impact on growth of its own policy settings. This includes a general crackdown on the Chinese private sector as well as what the Party has dubbed "reckless capital expansion" in the property sector and large technology firms. This has badly impacted business and investor confidence.

References:

[1][2] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents of the Central Plenary Session of the Party's National Congress since the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee of the Communist Party of China (Part I), 1997 Edition of the Central Literature Publishing House, pp. 2 and 36.

[3][19][27] Constitution of the People's Republic of China, 2004 edition of China Legal Publishing House, pp. 6, 32 and 35.

[4][7][8] Deng Xiaoping's Anthology, Volume 3, People's Publishing House, 1993 Edition, pp. 261, 23 and 91.

[5] The Party History Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Historical Events of the Communist Party of China in the New Era (1978.12-2002.5), 2002 Edition of the Central Party History Publishing House, p. 95.

[6] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents since the Twelfth National Congress (Part I), People's Publishing House, 1986 Edition, p. 258.

[9] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents since the Twelfth National Congress, People's Publishing House, 1988 Edition, p. 1237.

[10][11] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents since the 13th National Congress (Part I), 1991 edition of the People's Publishing House, pp. 32 and 216.

[12] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents since the 13th National Congress (middle), People's Publishing House, 1991 edition, p. 622.

[13][14] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents of the Central Plenary Session of the National Congress since the Fourth Plenary Session of the Thirteenth Central Committee of the Communist Party of China, 2002 edition of the Central Literature Publishing House, pp. 157 and 286.

[15] The Central Literature Research Office: Selected Important Documents since the 14th National Congress, People's Publishing House, 1996 Edition, p. 525.

[16][17] The Documentation Research Office of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China: Selected Important Documents since the 15th National Congress (Part I), People's Publishing House 2000, pp. 20 and 22.

[18][20] [21][22][23][24] Jiang Zemin Anthology, Volume 3, People's Publishing House, 2006 Edition, pp. 152, 151-152, 548, 540, 540, 572.

[25] Xinhua Monthly News Editor: Selected Important Documents of the Party and the State since the Sixth National Congress (Part I), People's Publishing House, 2005 Edition, p. 83.

[26] Decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on Several Issues Concerning Improving the Socialist Market Economy System (Guiding Reading), People's Publishing House, 2003 Edition, page 4.